

Oxidation of an antibiotic drug – fosfomycin disodium salt by chromium(VI) in aqueous perchloric acid medium – A kinetic and mechanistic study

L. N. Jattinagoudar, S. T. Nandibewoor and S. A. Chimatadar*

P.G. Department of Studies in Chemistry, Karnatak University, Pavate Nagar, Dharwad-580 003, Karnataka, India

E-mail : schimatadar@gmail.com

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Abstract : A detailed kinetic, mechanistic and spectroscopic investigation has been made on the oxidation of fosfomycin by potassium dichromate in aqueous perchloric acid medium at 25 °C and at a constant ionic strength, $I = 3.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The reaction products were identified and characterized by spectral studies such as GC-MS and IR. The reaction rate shows first order dependence on both chromium(VI) and fosfomycin concentrations and second order dependence on HClO_4 concentration. The addition of chromium(III), which is one of the reaction products, had no significant effect on the reaction rate. The effect of ionic strength and dielectric constant of the medium on the rate of reaction were studied. Based on the kinetic results, spectral evidences, stoichiometry of the reaction and product analysis, a suitable mechanism was proposed. The activation parameters were determined with respect to the slow step of the mechanism. The thermodynamic quantities were also determined and discussed.

Keywords : Kinetics, mechanism, oxidation, fosfomycin, chromium(VI).

Introduction

Potassium dichromate is a chromium salt or chromate and is a common metal making up a significant part of the earth's crust. Chromium and chromates occur naturally in our environment, including soil and water. They are also commonly found in products made of chrome and stainless steel, cement and leather. Chromium is one of the most abundant elements on earth and is naturally present in rocks, soil, plants, animals, volcanic dust and gases¹⁻⁴. It occurs in oxidation states ranging from -2 to +6⁵. Chromium(VI) is a strong oxidizing agent in acidic media. Chromium(VI) should have no unpaired electrons and have no color, but when bound to oxygen, charge transfer occurs from the O^{2-} . CrO_4 (chromate) has four oxygens which all charge transfer to the chromium giving orange color. In Cr_2O_7 (dichromate) one oxygen bridges between the two chromium atoms so each only gets charge transfer from three oxygens. $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ when combined with aqueous acid, forms chromic acid. Chromic acid is a strong dibasic oxidizing acid and is an oxoacid that has the molecular formula H_2CrO_4 and the structural formula :

The reactivity of chromium(VI) is determined by its oxidizing power. In acid solution, the reported reduction potential of the $\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}/\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}$ couple is 1.33 V⁶. Extensive kinetic and mechanistic studies on the oxidation of organic compounds by chromium reagents have revealed that reactions ordinarily involve a three electron change, whereby chromium(VI) species are reduced to chromium(III).

Fosfomycin (FOS) is the first phosphonate antibiotic isolated from *Streptomyces fradiae*. Phosphonates are characterized by direct, covalent phosphorus to carbon bonds instead of the carbon-oxygen-phosphorus (C-O-P) bond which is present in organic phosphate esters⁷. Phosphonates or phosphonic acids are organic compounds containing $\text{C-PO}(\text{OH})_2$ or $\text{C-PO}(\text{OR})_2$ groups.

Fosfomycin is an "old" antimicrobial that inhibits the first step of peptidoglycan synthesis and shows potent bactericidal action against many Gram-negative and Gram-

Fig. 1. First order plots of the oxidation of fosfomycin by chromium(VI) in aqueous perchloric acid medium at 25 °C; $[Cr^{VI}] \times 10^4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} = (1) 0.5; (2) 1.0; (3) 2.0; (4) 3.0; (5) 4.0; (6) 5.0$.

Fig. 2. UV-Visible spectral changes during the oxidation of fosfomycin by chromium(VI) in aqueous perchloric acid medium at 25 °C; $[Cr^{VI}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-4}$, $[fosfomycin] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$, $[HClO_4] = 3.0$ and $I = 3.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ with scanning time interval of 1.0 min.

first order dependence with respect to concentration of chromium(VI) (Table 1).

Effect of [fosfomycin] :

The concentration of fosfomycin was varied from $0.50 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ to $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at constant concentrations of chromium(VI), perchloric acid and ionic strength. It was found that the first order rate constants increased with increase in the concentration of fosfomycin (Table 1). From the slope of the plot of $\log k_{obs}$ versus $\log [FOS]$, the order with respect fosfomycin concentration was found to be unity (0.98). This is also confirmed by constant values of k_2 i.e. $k_{obs}/[fosfomycin]$ for variation of fosfomycin concentration (Table 1). The Michaelis-Menten plot of $1/k_{obs}$ against $1/[fosfomycin]$ at different temperatures was found to be linear with zero intercept (Fig. 5) indicating no complex formation between the reactants prior to the rate determining step.

Effect of [acid] :

The concentration of perchloric acid was varied from

Fig. 3. IR spectra of the product formyl phosphonic acid obtained during the oxidation of fosfomycin by chromium(VI).

Table 1. Effect of variation of chromium(VI), fosfomycin, perchloric acid concentrations on the chromium(VI) oxidation of fosfomycin in aqueous perchloric acid medium at 25 °C and $I = 3.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

$[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] \times 10^4$ (mol dm^{-3})	$[\text{Fosfomycin}] \times 10^3$ (mol dm^{-3})	$[\text{HClO}_4]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10$ (s^{-1})	$k_2 \times 10^3 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{Fosfomycin}]$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
0.5	2.0	3.0	1.17	–
1.0	2.0	3.0	1.10	–
2.0	2.0	3.0	1.18	–
3.0	2.0	3.0	1.19	–
4.0	2.0	3.0	1.08	–
5.0	2.0	3.0	1.07	–
2.0	0.50	3.0	0.31	0.60
2.0	1.0	3.0	0.59	0.59
2.0	2.0	3.0	1.18	0.59
2.0	3.0	3.0	1.73	0.57
2.0	4.0	3.0	2.25	0.56
2.0	5.0	3.0	3.11	0.62
2.0	2.0	0.25	0.02	–
2.0	2.0	0.5	0.05	–
2.0	2.0	1.0	0.19	–
2.0	2.0	1.5	0.27	–
2.0	2.0	2.0	0.45	–
2.0	2.0	2.5	0.93	–
2.0	2.0	3.0	1.18	–

Fig. 4. GC-MS spectra of the product formyl phosphonic acid.

Fig. 5. Michaelis-Menten plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{fosfomycin}]$ at (a) 45 °C, (b) 35 °C, (c) 25 °C, (d) 15 °C.

0.25 mol dm⁻³ to 3.0 mol dm⁻³ at constant concentrations of chromium(VI), fosfomycin, ionic strength and observed that the first order rate constants increased with increase in concentration of perchloric acid (Table 1). The order with respect to perchloric acid concentration was determined from the plot of k_{obs} versus $\log [\text{H}^+]$ and was found to be second order (1.7).

Effect of ionic strength (I) and dielectric constant of the medium (D) :

The effect of ionic strength on the rate of reaction was studied by varying the sodium perchlorate concentration at constant concentrations of chromium(VI), fosfomycin, HClO₄ the rate of reaction was found to increase with increase in the ionic strength. A plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $I^{1/2}$ is linear with positive slope (Fig. 6). At constant acidity and at other constant conditions, as the acetic acid content increases from 0–40% (v/v) in the reaction mixture, the k_{obs} values increased with increasing dielectric constant of the medium. Since the dielectric constants of aqueous acetic acid are not available in literature, they are computed from the values of pure liquids¹⁴. A plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/D$ was linear with positive slope (Fig. 6). No reaction of the solvent occurred with the oxidant under the experimental conditions employed. Thus from the observed experimental results, the rate law for the

reaction is given as follows :

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{chromium(VI)}]^{1.0} [\text{fosfomycin}]^{0.98} [\text{H}^+]^{1.70}$$

Effect of initially added products :

The effect of initially added products, chromium(III) and formyl phosphonic acid were studied in the 5.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ to 5.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ concentration range, keeping the ionic strength, reactant concentrations and other conditions constant. It was found that both chromium(III) as well as formyl phosphonic acid did not have any significant effect on the rate of reaction.

Polymerisation study :

The intervention of free radicals was examined by adding a known quantity of acrylonitrile to the reaction mixture and was kept in an inert atmosphere for 2 h. Upon diluting the reaction mixture with methanol, precipitate resulted, due to the polymerization of acrylonitrile, indicating the presence of free radical species in the mixture. Control experiments with fosfomycin or chromium(VI) did not show formation of precipitate.

Effect of temperature (T) :

The rate of reaction was measured at different temperatures, 15, 25, 35 and 45 °C under varying fosfomycin and acid concentrations. The rate was found to increase

Fig. 6. Effect of ionic strength and dielectric constant on the oxidation of fosfomycin by chromium(VI) at 25 °C.

with increasing temperature. The rate constants k of slow step of Scheme 1, were obtained from the intercepts of the plots of $[\text{fosfomycin}]/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{H}^+]^2$. The values of K , equilibrium step of Scheme 1 were obtained from the slopes of the plots of $[\text{fosfomycin}]/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{H}^+]^2$ (Fig. 7) at four different temperatures (Table 2). The energy of activation, E_a was evaluated from the slope of Arrhenius plot of $\log k$ versus $1/T$ (Table 2). The enthalpy of activation ΔH^\ddagger , the entropy of activation ΔS^\ddagger and the free energy of activation ΔG^\ddagger were obtained by using the Eyring eq.¹⁵.

$$k = \frac{k_B T}{h} e^{(-\Delta G^\ddagger/RT)} = \frac{k_B T}{h} e^{-(\Delta H^\ddagger + T\Delta S^\ddagger)/RT} \quad (2)$$

where k is the rate constant, k_B is the Boltzmann's constant, R is the gas constant, h is Planck's constant, T is the absolute temperature and ΔG^\ddagger is the free energy of activation.

Fig. 7. Verification of rate law (7) in the form of eq. (8).

The linear form of eq. (2) is

$$\ln \frac{k}{T} = - \frac{\Delta H^\ddagger}{RT} + \frac{\Delta S^\ddagger}{R} + \ln \frac{k_B}{h} \quad (3)$$

The van't Hoff plot ($\log K$ versus $1/T$) was drawn and the values of enthalpy of reaction (ΔH), entropy of reaction (ΔS) and free energy of reaction (ΔG), were calculated and given in Table 2. A comparison of ΔH value with ΔH^\ddagger obtained for the slow step of the reaction shows that these values mainly refer to the rate limiting step, sup-

Table 2

(a) Effect of temperature on the oxidation of fosfomycin by chromium(VI) in aqueous perchloric acid medium with respect to slow step of Scheme 1

Temp. (K)	$k \times 10$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)
288	0.42
298	2.54
308	2.86
318	4.55
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	56 ± 3
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	53 ± 3
ΔS^\ddagger (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-78 ± 4
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	76 ± 4
$\log A$	9.2 ± 0.03

(b) Thermodynamic quantities with respect to equilibrium step of Scheme 1

Temp. (K)	K ($\text{dm}^6 \text{mol}^{-2}$)
288	0.37
298	0.56
308	0.76
318	0.91
ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	23.3
ΔS (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	72.8
ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)	1.20

porting the fact that the reaction before the rate determining step is fast and involves low activation energy¹⁶.

Discussion

The reaction between chromium(VI) and fosfomycin has stoichiometry 1 : 1, with an apparent unit order in both fosfomycin and chromium(VI). As the perchloric acid concentration increases, the rate of reaction also increased (Table 1). The order with respect to perchloric acid concentration was found to be nearly two (1.7). No effects of initially added products were observed. The rate of reaction increased with increase in ionic strength and decreasing in dielectric constants were observed. These experimental results and the overall mechanism of possible mode of oxidation of fosfomycin are accommodated in the form of Scheme 1.

In the pre-equilibrium step, chromate reacts with two moles of acid to give H_2CrO_4 species, which is in accor-

Scheme 1

dance with the observed order of two in acid concentration. It is well known that in aqueous acid solution, chromium(VI) exists mainly in the form of acid chromate, H_2CrO_4 ¹⁷. In view of the observed order of unity in both chromate and fosfomycin concentrations, fosfomycin reacts with H_2CrO_4 in rate determining step to give a radical cation derived from fosfomycin and chromium(V) being generated. This intermediate chromium(V) reacts with the radical cation of fosfomycin in a fast step to give the 1-hydroxy-2-oxopropyl phosphonic acid and the intermediate chromium(IV) species. In a further fast step, chromium(IV) reacts with the formed 1-hydroxy-2-oxopropyl phosphonic acid to give the products chromium(III), formyl phosphonic acid and acetic acid. A free radical mechanism has been proposed¹⁸ for the oxidation of 2-propanol by chromium(VI) in aqueous acetic acid medium. Similarly the oxidation of fosfomycin by chromium(VI) occurs by the intervention of reactive chromium(V) and chromium(VI) species. The interven-

tion of chromium(V) is evident from the induction experiment with iodide¹⁸. The induced oxidation of iodide yields two equivalent of iodine for each equivalent of the inducer oxidized. The induction factor for iodide oxidation is nearly two, which indicates the active oxidizing agent is pentavalent chromium. The intervention of chromium(V) is evident from the progressive rate decrease in the presence of increasing amounts of added manganese(II) and the decrease reaches a limit of about one half of the rate found in the absence of manganese(II). Such results have also been obtained for chromium(VI) oxidation of 2-propanol in acetic acid¹⁸.

From Scheme 1, the rate law (7) can be derived as follows :

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4]}{dt} = k [\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4][\text{FOS}] \quad (4)$$

But, from first step of Scheme 1, we have,

$$[\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4] = K [\text{CrO}_4^{2-}][\text{H}^+]^2$$

Therefore,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4]}{dt} = kK [\text{CrO}_4^{2-}][\text{FOS}][\text{H}^+]^2 \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The total concentration of } [\text{CrO}_4^{2-}]_T \\ [\text{CrO}_4^{2-}]_T &= [\text{CrO}_4^{2-}]_f + [\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4] \\ &= [\text{CrO}_4^{2-}]_f + \{K [\text{CrO}_4^{2-}] + [\text{H}^+]^2\} \\ &= [\text{CrO}_4^{2-}]_f + \{1 + K [\text{H}^+]^2\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$[\text{CrO}_4^{2-}]_f = \frac{[\text{CrO}_4^{2-}]_T}{1 + K [\text{H}^+]^2} \quad (6)$$

where T and f stand for total and free respectively.

Substituting eq. (6) in (5) and omitting the subscripts we get,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{-d[\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4]}{dt} \\ &= \frac{kK [\text{CrO}_4^{2-}][\text{FOS}][\text{H}^+]^2}{1 + K [\text{H}^+]^2} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{CrO}_4^{2-}]} = \frac{kK [\text{FOS}][\text{H}^+]^2}{1 + K [\text{H}^+]^2} \quad (7)$$

The rate law (6) explains all the experimentally observed orders and it is rearranged to eq. (7), which is suitable for verification.

$$\frac{[\text{FOS}]}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{kK [\text{H}^+]^2} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (8)$$

According to eq. (8) the plot of L.H.S versus $1/[\text{H}^+]^2$ should be linear and is found to be so (Fig. 7). The intercept and the slope of such plot gives values of k and K respectively (Table 2).

$$(i) \text{ Intercept} = \frac{1}{k}$$

Therefore,

$$k = \frac{1}{\text{Intercept}} = 0.254 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$$

$$(ii) \text{ Slope} = \frac{1}{kK}$$

$$\begin{aligned} K &= \frac{1}{k \times \text{Slope}} = \frac{1}{0.254 \times 7.055} \\ &= 0.558 \text{ dm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2} \end{aligned}$$

The moderate values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger are both favorable for electron transfer processes. The observed modest enthalpy of activation as well as higher value of the rate constant of the slow step indicates that the oxidation presumably occurs via an inner-sphere mechanism. This conclusion is supported by the literature¹⁹. The effect of ionic strength on the rate of the reaction is contrary to that expected, in view of the high ionic strength ($I = 3.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) used in the experiments. Increase in the percentage of acetic acid decreases the dielectric constant of the medium, and this decrease in dielectric constant is responsible for the increase in the rate of the reactions. The plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/D$ is linear with positive slope. This fact can be explained by the reason acetic acid combines with chromic acid to form acetyl chromic acid or its protonated species which are stronger oxidizing agents than chromic acid alone²⁰. Similar observations have been reported by Sathyabhama *et al.*²⁰.

Conclusion

Kinetics and mechanism of chromium(VI) reduction by fosfomycin in aqueous perchloric acid media have been studied under the conditions $[\text{fosfomycin}] \gg [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$. In the acid media nearly second order in acid concentration is due to its involvement in the formation of H_2CrO_4 species. Under the kinetic conditions, the H_2CrO_4 species of Cr^{VI} has been found kinetically active. The reaction shows both first order dependence in $[\text{fosfomycin}]$ and $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$ and second order dependence in $[\text{H}^+]$ ion. The stoichiometry in oxidant to reductant is 1 : 1. The main oxidation product is formyl phosphonic acid which is characterized by UV-Visible, GC-MS and IR spectra and byproduct acetic acid is identified by spot test. Chromium(III) is confirmed by UV-Visible spectra. The added products chromium(III) and formyl phosphonic acid did not have effect on the rate of reaction. The activation

parameters and thermodynamic quantities were determined and discussed.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All chemicals were of analytical reagent grade, and double distilled water was used throughout this work. The chromium(VI) solution was prepared by dissolving $K_2Cr_2O_7$ (AR) in water. To study the effect of chromium(III) which is the reduced product, its solution was prepared by dissolving $Cr_2(SO_4)_3 \cdot K_2SO_4 \cdot 24H_2O$ (BDH, AR) in water. A stock solution of fosfomycin (Himedia) was prepared by dissolving sodium salt of fosfomycin in double distilled water. $HClO_4$ (70% Merck) and $NaClO_4$ were used to provide the required acidity and ionic strength respectively in the reaction medium. The $NaClO_4$ stock solution was prepared by careful neutralization of $HClO_4$ solution with NaOH solution. All the stock solutions were diluted as required before use.

Kinetic studies :

Pseudo-first order conditions were maintained for the kinetic runs, where the concentration of fosfomycin was much greater than that of dichromate and all the kinetic experiments were carried out at constant temperature at 25 ± 0.1 °C (unless otherwise specified) and at a constant ionic strength of $I = 3.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The reaction mixture containing fosfomycin which also contained the required concentrations of $HClO_4$ and $NaClO_4$ was taken in a conical flask and similarly, another conical flask containing dichromate alone were thermostatted in a water bath at 25 °C so as to attain the thermal equilibrium. The reaction was initiated by mixing these thermally equilibrated solutions of dichromate and fosfomycin. The progress of the reaction was followed spectrophotometrically at 360 nm as a function of time by monitoring the decrease in the absorbance of dichromate in a 1 cm cell placed in the thermostatted compartment of a Varian CARY 50 Bio UV-Visible spectrophotometer. There was no absorption from other species in the reaction mixture at this wavelength. The application of Beer's law under the reaction conditions was verified in the dichromate concentration range of $1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ to $10.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at 360 nm in 3.0 mol dm^{-3} perchloric acid. The molar absorptivity index of dichromate at 360

nm was found to be $\epsilon = 1300 \pm 20 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The kinetics was followed to more than 80% completion of the reaction, and good first order kinetics was observed. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , were calculated from the slopes of plots of the log (absorbance) versus time (Fig. 1). The pseudo-first order plots were linear to over 75% completion of the reaction. The spectral changes during the oxidation reactions are shown in Fig. 2.

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